

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESS THE FINANCIAL CONDITION OF ENTERPRISES AND SIGNS OF ECONOMIC INSOLVENCY

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Abstract

World financial crises have increased the number of bankruptcies in numerous countries and has resulted in a new area of research which responds to the need to predict this phenomenon, not only at the level of individual countries, but also at a global level, offering explanations of the common characteristics shared by the affected companies. Nevertheless, few studies focus on the prediction of bankruptcies globally. The aim of this paper is to conduct a literature review of corporate bankruptcy prediction models, on the basis of the existing international academic literature in the corresponding area. It primarily attempts to provide a comprehensive overview of literature related to corporate bankruptcy prediction, to investigate and address the link between the different authors (co-authorship), and to address the primary models and methods that are used and studied by authors of this area previously.

Keywords: bankruptcy, financial condition, economically insolvency.

Introduction

The deepening of the level of integration in the world economy in recent years has made it necessary to study more widely the factors affecting the financial condition of industrial enterprises, the organization and effective management of production in line with growing market demands. Nowadays, the rapid implementation of determining the financial condition of enterprises prevents them from becoming economically insolvent. This allows them to expand their activities using their own resources. It is almost impossible to increase the share of the real sector in GDP without improving the financial condition of enterprises. Software for assessing the financial condition of enterprises and identifying signs of economic insolvency provides practical assistance to financial managers of enterprises, their superiors in effectively monitoring the financial condition of enterprises.

Over the past 50 years, bankruptcy prediction has been a field of increasing interest to researchers all around the world. Many academic studies have been dedicated to exploring a corporate failure prediction model with the best accuracy. Since the breakthrough bankruptcy prediction model was introduced by Altman in 1968, a large body of research focuses on the prediction of corporate financial distress. In most cases, authors tend to use the ultimate failure (bankruptcy) as the dividing line when they distinguish the failed and non-failed firms. The exact definition of financial distress is not determined yet. From the perspective of theoretical analysis, financial distress has different degrees (Bruynseels & Willekens, 2012). Mild financial distress may be reflected as temporary cash flow difficulty, such as the concepts like insolvency, default and etc. The most serious one is called the business failure, or bankruptcy (Sun, Li, Huang & He, 2014). Business failure leads to the discontinuity of the firm's operation, and it has a significant effect on anyone who is related to the firm (creditors, stockholders, suppliers, among others). Consequently, the establishment of reliable business failure prediction models is of importance to

the current corporate firms (Zopounidis & Doumpos, 1999).

This study has been conducted based on research primarily using the database Scopus, considering the time frame from 1968 (the year when Altman published the Z-score model) to 2017. Twelve keywords (six primary and six secondary) were used to carry out the present literature review: Bankruptcy, Failure, Default, Distress, Early-warning, Insolvency, Score, Indicator, Ratio, Model, Prediction and Forecast. The outcome was a total of 36 combinations of keywords being used in this study so as to search the literature for framing the concept of bankruptcy prediction.

The main purpose of this study is to obtain a broader idea of the bankruptcy prediction concept, through identifying, critically evaluating and integrating findings of all relevant and high-quality studies using Scopus database. Furthermore, the trend of the development of bankruptcy prediction studies and the co-authorship among the main researchers in this area should be shown as well.

Other additional objectives are as follows:

- To observe the evolution of papers published during the years 1968-2017. (It should be noted that the year 2017 in this paper refers to a review done up to 31 December 2017)
- To identify the most frequently cited papers
- To identify the main journals in relation to the studied research field.
- To show the co-authorship among the main researchers in this area.
- To identify the most frequently used and studied models and methods in this area.

The literature review of bankruptcy prediction theories

In the literature, various authors define differently the failure of business in their studies. Dimitras, Zanakakis and Zopoudinis (1996) indicates that in the past and current investigations in business failure prediction area, scholars usually do their researches by studying some particular aspects or stages of business failure

process depending on their own experience or interests, without or with little reference to the theoretical framework. It causes that the literature of business failure is highly fragmented, as well as the ambiguity of the definition of business failure. According to Balcaen and Ooghe (2006), the criterion of failure is chosen arbitrarily in historical studies, whether a juridical definition of failure, namely bankruptcy (Altman, Marco & Varetto, 1994; Hillegeist, Zanakis & Zopoudinis, 2004; Wilson & Sharda, 1994; Fletcher & Goss, 1993; Lee, Han & Kwon, 1996), or a financial distress definition is used (Pan, 2012; Jones & Hensher, 2004; Sun & Li, 2008; Xiao, Yang, Pang & Dang, 2012).

The latter can also be described as failure-related events such as insolvency (Langford, Iyagba & Komba, 1993; Lepetit & Strobel, 2013; Jackson & Wood, 2013), default (Tserng, Chen, Huang, Lei & Tran, 2014; Peresetsky, Karminsky & Golovan, 2011), and etc. Meanwhile, Altman and Hotchikiss (2006) also comment that there are basically four genetic terms to describe those unsuccessful business enterprises which are failure, insolvency, default and bankruptcy.

According to the economic criteria, failure is interpreted by Altman and Hotchikiss (2006) as the realized rate of return on invested capital which is dramatically and continually lower than prevailing rates on equivalent investments taking risk into consideration. Insolvency takes place when the liabilities of a firm are greater than its assets. It makes a firm be incapable to meet its current obligations, sending a signal of a lack of liquidity (Altman & Hotchikiss, 2006). Default, literally occurs when a firm fails to fulfil an obligation, especially to pay a loan or appear in a low court. Using more corporate terms, default happens when the debtor violates a condition of an agreement with a creditor and can be the grounds for legal action. (Altman & Hotchikiss, 2006) Altman and Hotchikiss (2006) state that there are two types of bankruptcy. The first refers to the net worth position of an enterprise. The second type which is more observable refers to the firm's formal declaration in a federal district court, accompanied by a petition either to liquidate its assets or attempt a recovery program. While Ross, Westerfield and Jaffe (1999) concluded by summarizing the previous studies that there are three types of bankruptcy: legal bankruptcy, which literally means that the company goes to court for a declaration of bankruptcy; technical bankruptcy, which describes the situation that a company cannot fulfill the contract on schedule to repay principal and interest; and accounting-bankruptcy, which refers to the situation when a company is simply showing negative book net assets. Other authors investigate early warning signals which provides forecasting of bankruptcy risk of firms (Korol & Korodi, 2011). The word early warning was used originally in the military area, but now this concept is widely applied in some other fields such as: macroeconomics, business administration, environmental monitoring, and etc. Therefore, early warning of business failure is also an important term in the research field of bankruptcy prediction.

Since Altman published one of the most well-known bankruptcy prediction models in 1968, a multitude of bankruptcy prediction models have flooded the

literature (Gissel, 2007). It not only means the increasing number of papers published, but also the variety of the models used for business failure prediction. Thanks to the development of statistical techniques and information technology in recent years, more and more different predictive methods have been applied in order to establish a bankruptcy prediction model with a better accuracy. Altman's model in 1968 is a five-factor multivariate discriminant analysis model. According to Gissel (2007), the primary methods that have been used for model development are multivariate discriminant analysis (MDA), logit analysis, probit analysis, and neural networks. Especially from the 1990's, due to the fact that scholars are becoming more interested in artificial intelligence technology, neural network has become one of the most widely used promising tools. Applying this method, studies carried out by Tam and Kiang (1992), Altman et al. (1994), Wilson and Sharda (1994), Fletcher and Goss (1993), Lee et al. (1996) have had great influence on later research related to business failure prediction. Furthermore, Pan (2012) intended to optimise General Regression Neural Network model applying algorithm and obtained a good convergence results which indicates the good prediction capability of the model.

At the same time, there are also other methods based on machine learning and artificial intelligence adopted by many authors in bankruptcy prediction area, such as rough set (Beynon & Peel, 2001; Mckee, 2003; Xiao et al., 2012; Wang & Wu, 2017), case-based reasoning (Li & Sun, 2009; Li & Sun, 2011), support vector machine (Lin, Yeh & Lee, 2011; Li & Sun, 2012; Kim, 2011; Chandra, Ravi & Ravisankar, 2010) and so on. Rough set theory has been applied to a wide variety of financial decision analysis problems and it was created originally for dealing with the problem of apparent in discernibility between objects in a set. It has had a reported bankruptcy accuracy ranging from 76% to 88%. Case-based reasoning, as an effective and easily understandable method for solving real-world problems, has become a vital methodology in the current business failure prediction area due to its simplicity, competitive performance with modern methods, and ease of pattern maintenance (Lin et al., 2011). Support vector machine, arose from the area of statistical learning theory and was applied into business failure prediction for the first time in 2005 (Shin, Lee & Kim, 2005; Min & Lee, 2005), and proved to be superior to the performance of artificial neural network. (Kim, 2011). Since there is an increasing number of papers published related to business failure prediction from year 2000 and some other authors shed light on carrying out overviews or comparison of the business failure prediction models. Hillegeist et al. (2004) compare two accounting-based models, Altman's (1968) Z-score and Ohlson's (1980) O-score, with a market-based model developed by themselves based on Black-Scholes-Merton optionpricing model, showing that the latter can provide significantly more information than the former two. Balcaen and Ooghe (2006) undertake an overview of classic statistical methodologies in the recent 35 years, in order to understand their features as well as their related problems.

This monumental research task has generated a wide variety of models, supported in turn by very diverse methodologies. One of the paths initially taken by the literature was the development of models that had been built from a sample of companies belonging to several sectors and which, therefore, could be considered as off-center models (Casey and Bartczak, 1985; Odom and Sharda, 1990; Altman et al., 1994; Wilson and Sharda, 1994). The development of these off-center models has been important throughout time, predominantly those built using samples of medium and large companies from different sectors (Charalambous, Chatitou and Kaourou, 2000; Chen, Härdle and Moros, 2011; Sangjae and Wu, 2013). The literature on bankruptcy prediction also highlights the development of models based on samples of companies belonging to specific sectors of activity, which have been called centered models. The most popular of the centered models is the one used for credit institutions (Santomero and Vinso, 1977; Martindel-Brio and Serrano-Cinca, 1995; Alam et al., 2000). Another of the most popular centered models has been used for industrial companies (Altman, 1968; Diamond, 1976; Appetiti, 1984; Zavgren, 1985; Grover, 2003). Recently, models have also been developed focusing on companies from other sectors, such as Internet companies (Wang, 2004), hospitality companies (Park and Hancer, 2012; Fernández, Cisneros and Callejón, 2016), agricultural companies (Mateos-Ronco et al., 2011), construction companies (Gill de Albornoz and Giner, 2013), and commercial and service companies (Keener, 2013).

Over the past two decades, research on financial stress and solvency risk has begun to allow for more precise analysis thanks to the emergence and further development of artificial neural networks, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. In particular, Odom and Sharda for the first time used the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) methodology to predict the bankruptcy of American companies using the same financial indicators as in Altman's research. Their results showed a higher accuracy compared to the Multiple Linear Discriminant Model (MDA). Over time, many studies have confirmed that ANN methods are effective methods for identifying financial distress and bankruptcy risk from logistic regression and MDA.

Financial statement analysis is an integral and important part of the broader field of business analysis, and business analysis is the process of evaluating a company's economic prospects and risks. It includes analysis of the company's business environment, its strategies, financial position and performance. Business analysis is useful for a wide range of business decisions, such as whether to invest in stocks or debt securities, whether to lend through short-term or long-term loans, how to value a business in an initial public offering (IPO), and how to evaluate restructuring, including mergers, acquisitions acquisition and allocation.

Financial statement analysis is the application of analytical tools and techniques to general purpose financial statements and related data to derive ratios and conclusions useful in business analysis. Financial state-

ment analysis reduces reliance on guesswork and intuition when making business decisions. As a result, it reduces the uncertainty of business analysis. However, this does not reduce the need for expert opinion, but instead creates a systematic and effective basis for business analysis. Proper analysis and interpretation of data is critical to good business analysis. This is the role of financial statement analysis. Through it, the analyst better understands and interprets both qualitative and quantitative financial data, so that reliable conclusions can be drawn about the company's prospects and risks.

A detailed analysis of the literature on bankruptcy prediction allows us to observe the existence of a definite pattern regarding the building of off-center models as opposed to centered models, with the former being much more numerous than the latter. However, it is not possible to draw a definite conclusion on the superiority of one type of model over another (Bellovary, Giacomo and Akers, 2007). The absence of a practical conclusion on the superiority of a centered model over an off-center model may be due to the fact that one type of model and another could not be compared homogeneously due to the disparity of methodologies, approaches, available databases, time periods and countries, among other issues. Therefore, the existence of this gap in the literature, which does not make it possible to elucidate the superiority of off-center models over centered models, is an important research issue that this work seeks to solve. To this end, this work has selected different samples of Spanish companies that were and were not in bankruptcy in the 2010-2015 period.

As can be seen from the preceding section, the prediction of business insolvency is an area which has been extensively studied over time, although the majority of existing studies are characterised by their reference to a specific industry or a determined country, with very few global studies; that is, those using companies from different countries as a reference.

Among the studies that are global there are, in turn, different focuses, and not all of them focus exclusively on the concept of bankruptcy. The objective of a large part of these studies has been to check the effectiveness of the different prediction models. Thus, (Pindado et al., 2008) developed a model to estimate the probability of financial difficulties using technical panel data. This study used the data from a sample of firms from the G-7 countries to obtain an indicator of the probability of financial difficulties that includes the specific nature of each firm. (Chen et al. 2011), used a sample of Polish and Australian firms, proposing a bankruptcy prediction model based on the diffuse adaptation method of k-nearest neighbour. Their results confirmed that the proposed model allows the identification of the most significant financial ratios.

The proposed model managed to correctly predict 92.5% and 92.1% of the training and testing samples, respectively, using financial information from the two-year period prior to bankruptcy. Their conclusions suggest that European industrial firms that are less capitalised, that fail to generate sufficient resources to meet their short-term financial debt, that have low profitability and that are small in size have been most likely to

suffer bankruptcy in the current financial crisis. (Tsai et al 2014), with firms from Australia, Germany and Japan, performed a comparative study of the effectiveness of different classifiers, such as MLP, SVM and DT, on the basis of well-known combination methods such as voting, bagging and boosting. The results show that DT combined with boosting is the technique that offers the greatest accuracy. (Liang et al 2015) used a sample of Taiwanese and Chinese firms and researched the effect of the selection of the prediction models' variables using different classification techniques such as MDA, t-test, Logit, genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimisation. The results demonstrated that no single best methodological combination exists. (Ferreira et al 2016) used hazard models in order to ascertain which factors determine a greater probability of financial distress for small and medium sized firms in Europe, and suggest that the location and number of shareholders are important indicators. Other international studies have focused on studying the financial difficulties of banks in different countries. For example, (Chauhan et al 2009) apply NN to a sample of US, Turkish and Spanish banks, using the data management group method. (Maghyreh et al 2014) and (Betz et al 2014) apply Logit for banks in countries of the Gulf Cooperation Council and Europe, respectively.

Lastly, only two studies have had as their objective the comparison of models created for specific regions of the world (Korol T 2013). The paper focused on studying industrial firms in financial difficulties in the United States, Europe and Asia (Laitinen et al 2000). To do this they used Logit and corresponding data one year before the situation of financial difficulty of the companies. Their conclusions indicate that regional models are superior to global models and that the differences between the regional models constructed are related to factors such as imports and exports between the countries, labour conditions and the macroeconomic setting. The study by Korol (2013) uses companies in the legal position of bankruptcy and compares the effectiveness of different prediction models between two regions, namely Latin-America (Mexico, Argentina, Brazil, Chile and Peru) and Central Europe (Poland). He builds a bankruptcy risk model with a time horizon of two years, using MDA, DT and NN, and a set of 14 financial ratios as possible predictive variables. He reached the conclusion that type I errors are greater in the Latin- American firms than the European firms, and that DT is the model which is most effective in both samples.

The above research also has other shortcomings. Firstly, global bankruptcy prediction models barely exist. The aforementioned study by Korol (2013) compares the predictive power of different techniques in two regions, but does not construct a global model capable of predicting in the different regions of the world. Similarly, the study by Platt (2008), although it tests the accuracy of a global model in different regions, does so from a wider perspective of financial distress that covers companies in financial difficulties but fails to focus on bankrupt companies. And secondly, there is a need for a precise evaluation of global models using procedures that value not only the adjustment of the

model but also its complexity. The bankruptcy prediction models for Asia mainly consist of three variables: Earnings/ Total assets, Retained earnings/Total assets and Total debt/Total assets. As such, they select as the best bankruptcy predictors the variables that refer to profitability and debt. In the case of the models for Europe, the significant variables turned out to be Earnings/ Total assets, Current assets/Current liabilities, EBIT/Total assets, Total debt/ Total assets and Current assets/Total assets. Hence, the aspects of profitability, debt and liquidity turned out to be more important when predicting bankruptcy in European firms.

For the models constructed with American companies, the significant variables refer to liquidity, profitability, efficiency and debt. More specifically, the following variables were chosen: Working capital/Total assets, EBIT/Total assets, Sales/Total assets, and Total debt/ Total assets.

The global models are formed by the variables Current assets/Current liabilities, Working capital/Total assets, EBIT/Total assets, Sales/Total assets, Total debt/ Total assets, and Current assets/Total assets. These global models also cover aspects of liquidity, profitability, efficiency and debt, but the set of variables for t-1, t-2, and t-3 do not coincide with any of the regional models.

All of the models constructed attain a high percentage of accuracy (greater than 80%). Moreover, both the Omnibus test and the Hosmer and Lemeshow test, and the R2 indicate that the goodness-of-fit of the estimate of these is acceptable. The area beneath the ROC curve (in all cases very close to 1) confirms that the four models correctly classify bankrupt firms and non-bankrupt firms.

In all of the models, were selected number of criterias: Working capital/Total assets, EBIT/Total assets, Current assets/ Total assets, and Region. As such, in addition to the geographical location, the aspects of liquidity and profitability are also represented.

Conclusions and Implications

The recent Our evidence helps to explain that the globalisation process extends from the financial characteristics of firms to the factors that cause bankruptcy. These conclusions may be important when minimising the cost of constructing bankruptcy prediction models, given the existence of explanatory financial variables which are common to the most important regions in the world. In addition, and due to the power of generalisation demonstrated by the global model, we emphasise the need for multinational firms to manage their own bankruptcy prediction models, applying them to clients, suppliers and the firms in which they have holdings. Lastly, the existence of a global model for bankruptcy prediction can also meet the requirements of International Standards on Auditing with respect to the going concern principle, which proposes the use of feasibility models for firms in order to support auditors' opinions in the context of risk assessment.

Like all research, this study has some limitations, mainly the availability of firms data in emerging countries. Given that it is research undertaken from a global perspective, it requires a much greater scope of information in comparison to other studies performed in this

field. In addition, future research could set an approach to investigate which macro conditions affect the behavior of the financial variables that have proved as good predictors bankruptcy in this paper. Finally, to increase the generalizability of the results, data from other firms (i.e., small and medium-sized enterprises) should be included.

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